

FASHION aLIVE

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	6.3
TITLE	Kick-off meeting minutes
DUE DATE	Month 3
ACTUAL DATE OF DELIVERY TO EC	14 November 2022

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Executive Summary

This report contains the minutes of the kick off meeting held on November 11, 2022, including the meeting's agenda and the topics discussed. It also includes the presentations that were shared within the meeting.

List of attendants

ORGANISATION	NAME	FUNCTION
CREAMODITE	Gisela Fortuna	Project Coordinator
CREAMODITE	Martina Gesell	Project Manager
UMINHO	Ana Cristina Broega	Project Manger
UMINHO	Joana Cunha	Senior Researcher
UMIHO	Inês do Amaral	Junior Researcher
UCAMPANIA	Roberto Liberti	Project Manager
UCAMPANIA	Ornella Cirillo	Senior Researcher
UCAMPANIA	Chiara Scarpitti	Senior Researcher
UCAMPANIA	Vincenzo Cirillo	Senior Researcher
XSENTRIK	Yilmaz Vurucu	Senior Expert
INNOCAS	Irene Solé	Coordinator Contact (CREAMODITE)

MEETING LOCATION	Online (videoconference)
Start time	11.00 hs CET
End time	13.30 hs CET

Title 1

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Title 2

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Annex I: Kick off meeting presentation prepared by CREAMODITE

FASHION ALIVE

KICK-OFF MEETING

CREAMODITE | UCAMPANIA | UMINHO
XSENTRIK ARTS | INNOCAS

11.11.2022

Funded by the
European Union

PURPOSE OF THE K.O.M

- Progress report by partner
- Work package overview
- Milestones and deliverables
- Internal organisation + next steps
- Q&A

PROGRESS REPORT

CREAMODITE

- ❑ Admin/financial/coordination of the project
- ❑ A series of experimental methods to reach the so-called Zero Waste Fashion Concept
- ❑ Generate knowledge on new systems to design clothes aiming at producing zero or little waste when manipulating materials and garments
- ❑ Design patternmaking methods where the textile material is no longer pre-defined by the body shape, fitting flat pattern pieces like a jigsaw puzzle so no fabric is wasted
- ❑ A capsule collection of 15-20 pieces using Zero Waste Fashion Methods

PROGRESS REPORT

UCAMPANIA

- ❑ Research experimental sustainable fashion from a cultural perspective, analysing the heritage frame of craft textile manufactures typical and ancient textile techniques of the Campania region. Experiment with innovative approaches using advanced digital technologies
- ❑ Transdisciplinary vision that connects contemporary art, textile manipulation, advanced manufacturing processes to investigate a circular fashion system through the hybridization of artisanal techniques and software
- ❑ A capsule collection of 15-20 pieces

PROGRESS REPORT

UMINHO

- ❑ Will centre their creations around sustainable materials and the concept of circular fashion, experimenting with new business models that allow for the reuse of discarded fabrics
- ❑ Explore the possibilities of extending the life of stopped fabrics stockpiles, leftovers or small rolls of fabric/scrap, pre-existing clothing
- ❑ Develop an awareness and recollection campaign to increase the conscientious disposal of end-of-life clothing
- ❑ A capsule collection of 15-20 pieces using recycled fabrics

PROGRESS REPORT

XSENTRIK ARTS

- ❑ Will be in constant communication with the rest of the partners to understand their creations and philosophy, with the aim to create the best digital strategy
- ❑ Conceptualise the videomapping structure considering theme of the videos, storytelling, matching imagery, locations, music and sound, shooting and filming strategy, etc
- ❑ Website, social media & communications
- ❑ Design and create media contents

WORK PACKAGES

WP1 – MANAGEMENT, ADMINISTRATION AND COORDINATION – CREAMODITE

OBJECTIVES

- To ensure the success of the project through appropriate coordination of the organizational, technological, methodological and financial activities
- To ensure consensus and clarity within the consortium regarding reporting process, risk management, contracts, conflicts and other issues
- To ensure the quality of the work performed

WORK PACKAGES

WP2 – CAPACITY BUILDING THROUGH EXPERIMENTAL SUSTAINABLE FASHION METHODS – CREAMODITE, UCAMPANIA, UMINHO

OBJECTIVES

- ❑ To explore and experiment on new sustainable fashion methods via 3 different strategies
- ❑ To develop new producing methods that comply with the sustainability approach
- ❑ To create 3 collections of 15-20 fashion pieces each produced with the innovative strategies

WORK PACKAGES

WP3 – CREATIVE EXPRESSION THROUGH DIGITAL INNOVATION APPLIED TO CULTURAL EVENTS – XSENTRIK ARTS

OBJECTIVES

- To design new digital strategies to be applied at a fashion show
- To create the contents for a videomapping projection and source of music that fits the fashion show, sourcing feedback from Creamodite and the universities
- To integrate the digital strategies and videomapping with each of the 3 premises where the shows will take place, considering heights, lights, projection, sounds and echoes, sizes, etc

WORK PACKAGES

WP4 – KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND AUDIENCE ENGAGEMENT THROUGH FASHION & CULTURE EVENTS – CREAMODITE,
UCAMPANIA, UMINHO, XSENTRIK ARTS

OBJECTIVES

- To plan, organise and undertake three different fashion shows to exhibit the sustainable collections generated in WP2
- To plan and prepare the artistic direction of the shows including the performance and choreography, as well as the roundtables and relevant topics
- To integrate the digital strategies according to results of WP3
- To prepare a satisfaction survey to be handed out to the public for evaluation of results

WORK PACKAGES

WP5 – IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND NEXT STEPS – CREAMODITE, UCAMPANIA, UMINHO, XSENTRIK ARTS

OBJECTIVES

- To understand and evaluate the project results
- To generate a report on the learnings on the sustainable fashion methods and the undertaking of the innovative fashion events, including potential areas to improve
- To discuss next steps and potential conversion into a future collaborative project

WORK PACKAGES

WP6 – COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION – CREAMODITE, UCAMPANIA, UMINHO, XSENTRIK ARTS

OBJECTIVES

- To efficiently communicate information to the public about the project and its implementation status
- To coordinate communication between consortium members and the public through dedicated project website and social media platforms
- To maximise the project impact through recurrent and effective communications actions

WORK PACKAGES

STAFF EFFORT PER PARTICIPANT

Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	Total person/months
CREAMODITE	7.5	7.9	0.6	17.40	1.5	3.1	38
UMINHO	1.6	9.7	0.4	8.0	0.4	2.6	22.7
UCAMPANIA	2.4	7.9	0.3	4.4	0.4	2.7	18.1
XSENTRIK ARTS	1.6	0.9	9.4	2.8	0.7	2.2	17.6
Total person/months	13.1	26.4	10.7	32.6	3.0	10.6	96.4

MILESTONES & DELIVERABLES

NOV 2022

- ❑ **D6.3** – Kick-off Meeting – ALL PARTNERS ✓
- ❑ **D6.1** – C&D Plan: all relevant information regarding the C&D strategy to follow during the project execution: including objective public, tactical action plan, communication actions, visual identity, social media strategies, events attendance, etc. – XSENTRIK ARTS ✓
- ❑ **D6.4** – Website and social media established – XSENTRIK ARTS ✓

JAN 2023

- ❑ Travel to see the locations (Italy, Portugal)
- ❑ **MS2** – Video-mapping strategy generated: Video available and shared with all partners (MEETING TO REVIEW VIDEOMAPPING)

MILESTONES & DELIVERABLES

MARCH 2023

- ❑ **MEETING** to plan for the event story telling and contents of the show, choreographic design, presentation/contents to be discussed in the round tables, public survey/questionnaire to report on the events performance – **ALL**
- ❑ **MS3** – Strategy for integration defined: Final budget and technical plan for equipment for each event – **XSENTRIK ARTS**

APRIL 2023

- ❑ **D4.1** – Plan for the event story telling and contents of the show, choreographic design: This document will be necessary for all partners to plan the events accordingly – **CREAMODITE, UCAMPANIA, UMINHO**
- ❑ **D4.3** – Presentations/contents to be discussed in the roundtables: At least one agenda per each roundtable session will be shared, containing from one side details of the project as a whole and from the collection presented, and then from the other side, there will be specific contents related to the fashion collection – **CREAMODITE, UCAMPANIA, UMINHO**
- ❑ **D3.2** – Report on the digital strategy chosen for each of the fashion events: all the details of the tools to be used, as well as the specifications of the locations of the events – **XSENTRIK ARTS**
- ❑ **D3.3** – Report on the integration strategy onto fashion and cultural events: how will the digital contents be applied to the fashion events – **XSENTRIK ARTS**

MILESTONES & DELIVERABLES

APRIL 2023

- ❑ **D1.1** – Internal progress report: First report collecting a general overview of the first year of the project. The report will contain an update on the overall progress by each WP and task, including the key achievements and next expected steps. A financial control report will also be included. The report shall be brief, but concise and provide the relevant information about the project progress. **CREAMODITE**

MAY 2023

- ❑ **D2.1** – Collections portfolio Zero Waste Fashion: including the information (written and graphic) of each fashion piece, as well as the description of the methods tested and achieved to produce the designs. -**CREAMODITE**
- ❑ **D2.2** – Collections portfolio Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Fashion: including the information (written and graphic) of each fashion piece, as well as the description of the methods tested and achieved to produce the designs. -**UCAMPANIA**
- ❑ **D2.3** – Collections portfolio Circular Fashion: including the information (written and graphic) of each fashion piece, as well as the description of the methods tested and achieved to produce the designs. -**UMINHO**
- ❑ CREAMODITE Round Tables: 18 may 2023
- ❑ CREAMODITE Fashion Show: 19 may 2023

MILESTONES & DELIVERABLES

JUNE 2023

- ❑ **D3.1** - Videos for videomapping and other digital contents will be available in the project website (once it is up), in the project social media (once it is setup), as well as in the partners own websites and social media.
- ❑ **UMINHO EVENT** - TBC

JULY 2023

- ❑ **UCAMPANIA EVENT** - TBC

AUG 2023

- ❑ **D4.2** - Public Survey/questionnaire. Report on the events performance: A report on the performance of the events will be prepared with all the insights and conclusions. It will be informed by the satisfaction questionnaire handed to public. **ALL**

[VIEW FULL PROJECT SCHEDULE & DELIVERABLES SPREADSHEET >>>>](#)

NEXT STEPS

INTERNAL PROJECT ORGANISATION

#1 SHARED PROJECT FOLDER

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1LYMEXBukBOWbkIFjgVr3YFeCern9AEIT?usp=share_link

- ❑ Upload social media + blog post content (include images, video, etc... plus a short description of what the content is about in separate folders) – **IDEALLY WEEKLY UPDATES.**
- ❑ University logos - https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1bGMDI072acWllRo7aDnToopRWtAA-1QX?usp=share_link
- ❑ EU logos - https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1FwwC.JlRke4XOK6OGsHX7rxFlIE8wDvMe?usp=share_link
- ❑ Project templates (social media, report, presentations)
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1S0B1pFnGmmaGffB65wnfpTrCi7-Uctmr?usp=share_link
- ❑ Music & ideas for videomapping:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PefShmiVINhJblyD7lKDnA_k5OYU9ixQ?usp=share_link

NEXT STEPS

INTERNAL PROJECT ORGANISATION

#2 CONFIRM FASHION SHOW DATES & LOCATIONS

All partners are expected to participate in round tables/press conferences (day 1) and attend each other's fashion shows (day 2)

- ❑ Creamodite: 18-19 may 2023
- ❑ Ucampania: July 2023 (TBC)
- ❑ Uminho: June 2023 (TBC)

NEXT STEPS

INTERNAL PROJECT ORGANISATION

#3 TRAVEL PLANS

Xsentrik + Martina are travelling to see the locations for the event + take measurements for the videomapping installation

- Creamodite: 2-3 october
- Ucampania: TBC*
- Uminho: TBC*

**ideally January 2023 after the holidays*

NEXT STEPS

INTERNAL PROJECT ORGANISATION

#4 COMMUNICATIONS AND DISSEMINATION

Xsentrik Arts is the Communications Leader, but ALL PARTNERS are supposed to engage in C&D actions (social media, press, academic events, publications, etc)

- ❑ Website: <https://www.fashion-alive.com>
- ❑ Instagram: [@fashion_alive_22](https://www.instagram.com/fashion_alive_22)
- ❑ Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/fashionalive22>
- ❑ Provide comms & social media contact for each UNI

👉 Please follow, like & tag us

NEXT STEPS

INTERNAL PROJECT ORGANISATION

#5 PAYMENTS & FINANCIAL REPORTING

- Initial payment – 40%
- 2nd payment – 40% April 2023 (after internal financial report)
- Technical justification: Reporting via EC online platform (template available)
- Financial/costs justification: Timesheets (template), job contracts, payrolls, proof of payment, calculation of daily rate, methodology, costs tracking, travel costs (keep records and justificative documents), invoices (stamp, concept), proof of payment. ***COPY OF THESE RECORDS MUST BE UPLOADED TO PROJECT FOLDER TO BE KEPT ON FILE FOR FUTURE AUDITS***

QUESTIONS, DOUBTS, COMMENTS?

Annex II: Kick off meeting presentation prepared by UCAMPANIA

V: Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli
Dipartimento di Architettura e Design Industriale

Fashion Alive
Project

FASHION ALIVE
Creative Europe Project

Development of new audiences via innovative cultural and digital strategies to promote experimental sustainable fashion methods

PARTNERS:

Creamodite Asociacion
Para La Constitucion Y
Reestructuracion De
Empresas De Moda
Diseño Y Tecnologia
(Madrid, Spagna)

Universidade Do Minho
(Guimarães, Portugal)

Università Degli Studi
Della Campania
Luigi Vanvitelli
(Aversa, Italia)

Xsentrikarts
Platform For Arts
(Vienna, Austria)

- The main approach of the **Fashion Alive Project is the promotion of sustainable practices in the fashion industry through the creation of events to involve a wider public and raise awareness on this issue.** The **Fashion Alive Project** approach is therefore supported by three different partners: On the one hand, **Creamodite** (*Spain*), **Uminho** (*Portugal*) and **Unicampania** (*Italy*) will conceptualise and experiment the creation of sustainable fashion methods, where each partner will work on a specific innovative methodology. In the same time, **Xsentrik** (*Austria*) will explore and envisage a digital and audiovisual strategy using technological tools (*a combination of video, 3D projections, video mapping software, sound, light and music created by artificial intelligence*).
- The creations of the four partners will be exhibited to the public during three experimental fashion and art events that will **combine the exhibition/catwalk** of the sustainable creations of Creamodite, Uminho and Unicampania with the digital and audiovisual creations of Xsentrik, as well as other added artistic actions such as live performances conceived by an artistic director, urban dances designed by a professional Spanish choreographer and drone filming. The events will take place on two different days, as there will be a more participative session with round tables, talks, lectures and public discussions on art, sustainability, fashion and creativity. After the presentation of the sustainable fashion projects devised by the different partners, they will carry out an analysis to assess the impact gathered through the innovative events realised in the 3 different countries involved in the European project (*Spain, Italy, Portugal*), in order to understand how the message of sustainable fashion reaches the general public through this type of innovative project expressions.

Fashion alive events

Spain

Roundtable 18 May 2023

Fashion Show 19 May 2023

(Video Mapping XSENTRIK, Fashion Show Madrid, Spagna)

Portugal

Fashion Show Giugno 2023

(Video Mapping XSENTRIK, Fashion Show Università Minho Guimaraes, Portogallo)

Italy

Fashion Show Luglio 2023

(Video Mapping XSENTRIK, Chostro di San Lorenzo, Fashion Show Chostro di San Lorenzo, Aversa, Italia)

Research Unit UniCampania

The Unicampania research unit of the European project Fashion Alive - composed of lecturers Roberto Liberti, Omella Cirillo, Chiara Scarpitti and Vincenzo Cirillo - is proposing an experimental brief for the Design Laboratories, Fashion Setting, History of Fashion of the Three-year degree course in Fashion Design and the courses of Design for Cosmetics and History of Contemporary Fashion of the curriculum in Fashion Eco Design of the Master's degree course in Design for Innovation, which each lecturer will be able to decline in the individual course programmes.

The individual courses will deal with research into experimental sustainable fashion from the point of view of cultural heritage, analysing typical handcraft textile manufactures in the Campania region, and the heritage framework of ancient textile techniques. Various innovative approaches will be experimented in the different courses, using advanced digital technologies, with which to give continuity to the trousseau tradition. Moving around a transdisciplinary vision that connects different knowledges - such as fashion and contemporary art, textile manipulation, advanced production processes - the work will investigate an experimental circular fashion system through the hybridisation of particular craft techniques or innovative software, in order to develop new creative industries, with the aim of spreading a transdisciplinary fashion culture.

SELECTION OF RESULTS:

The prototypes will be clothes, accessories, selected by an internal Unicampania jury for participation in the FASHION ALIVE SHOW scheduled for July 2023.

CLOSING EVENT: July 2023

Closing event FASHION ALIVE the result of research on Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Fashion (researched, produced, designed and owned by UNICAMPANIA) CHIOSTRO DI SAN LORENZO AD SEPTIMIUM AVERSA

Fashion Laboratories Involved In The Development Of Collections And Other Courses Involved:

- Laboratori Di Design Per La Moda Unicompania 1 Anno / 2 Anno / 3 Anno _ Triennale
- Fashion Skills_ Triennale
- Laboratori Di Disegno_ triennale
- Abilita' Per La Rappresentazione Digitale_ triennale
- Tecnologie E Materiali Per Il Fashion Design_ triennale
- Fondamenti Visivi Del Progetto_ triennale
- Scenari Avanzati Della Moda 1 Anno _ Magistrale
- Fashion Eco-Design 1 Anno _ Magistrale
- Fashion Eco-Design 2 Anno _ Magistrale

Hypothesis Involvement Of Other Fashion Courses To Complement The Project

Drawing Workshops

They will be able to redesign and graphically reinterpret specific contemporary figurines related to the Fashion Alive Brief.

They will also be able to give the guidelines for the representation and breakdown of the garments and outfits examined (particularly of the first year).

Three-year and Master's courses in Fashion History

They will be able to assist design courses for traditional techniques to be used for contemporary collections contemporary collections, for archive research on traditional outfits from Campania, and for everything that can constitute the basis for the various collection briefs. The search for original materials will flow into the selection of garments which will be variously used in the collections and the creation of an archive of images (for the realisation of VIDEO) and a sound archive (to be used for an audio for the final event).

The Fashion Setting courses *(deadline FEBRUARY 2023)*

will be able to work on the preparation of project ideas for the final fashion show in JULY 2023 which will take place in the cloister of the Department of Architecture and Industrial Design in Aversa. The catwalk, the project idea with sustainable materials for the event, the seating (in recycled wood, low environmental impact polystyrene, etc.) the design of lighting, and sound can be the starting theme of the courses.

The Design for Cosmetics course

will be able to work on the theme of whiteness and experimentation already underway with a company from Campania producing cosmetic lines derived from milk.

Technologies and materials for fashion design

You will be able to work on colour and material folders for eco-sustainable fashion collections starting from the natural colours of linen or cotton starting from pieces of kit tracked down by the course students themselves.

From traditional corredo to an experimental capsule collection

Project Brief

The collection proposed starts from the concept of reuse, upcycling, and creative design with a view to the conscious development of a fashion collection.

Starting from traditional Campanian linen, cotton, silk or hemp, which individual groups of students will be able to recover as raw material, the Project aims at the creation of a capsule collection of clothes/accessories.

The theme of White and its chromatic declinations will therefore be the fil rouge that will unite the different clothing collections in the individual years.

This can be combined with a colour that is in any case derived from the trousseau tradition (*e.g. the blue and red typical of the*

letters/initials embroidered on traditional trousseaux), or black.

Thus, starting from nightshirts, dishcloths, table linen, curtains, sheets, etc. of traditional trousseaus, textile garments and accessories will be produced using innovative or traditional prototyping techniques, according to the choice of the individual course teachers.

STEP 1

Materials Research / Recovery

> October

Collection of linen, cotton, hemp, silk corredo from local vintage markets and students' families (curtains, tablecloths, linen sheets, nightgowns, cotton shirts, collars, dishcloths, etc.)

STEP 2

Upcycling / Textile Handling

> November/ January

> March / May

Creation of capsule collections and realisation of prototypes

STEP 3

Garment Selection / Event

> June/ July

Preparation Fashion Show and selection of garments made by the students.

Triennial Fashion Design: 60/80 garments

Magistral Curr. Fashion Eco Design: 10 garments

Suggested Techniques

Deconstruction and sartorial reconstruction

Draping

Moulage

Patchwork

Unravelling

Manual embroidery

Industrial embroidery

Stencyl print

Digital printing

Hand printing

Natural dyeing

Palette Colori

Rei Kawakubo **ESEMPI**

Lessico Familiare **ESEMPI**

Simon Cracker ^{ESEMPI}

Niccolo Pasqualetti

ESEMPI

Cappe in lino realizzate a partire da un vecchio corredo di lenzuola in lino. **ESEMPI Progetto Procida (Liberti, Fiorentino, Cirillo)**

UPCYCLING - SOVRAPPOSITION

IL METODO DI PIEGATURA DEGLI ORIGAMI INCONTRA LE TRAME DI LINO

- #1 FASCIATURO
60x112
-FRONTE RETRO USUALI
-FRONTE CON RICAMI
- #2 ASCIUGAMANO
60x112
-FRONTE 10CM
-FRONTE RETRO USUALI
-FRONTE CON RICAMI
- #3 FEDERA
47x68
-FRONTE RETRO USUALI
-FRONTE CON RICAMI

UPCYCLING - DISASSEMBLY

IL METODO DI PIEGATURA DEGLI ORIGAMI INCONTRA LE TRAME DI LINO

#1 CAMICIA DA NOTTE

60x112
-FRONTE RETRO USUALI
-FRONTE CON RICAMI

V. Disegnato da A. ...

UPCYCLING - MANIPULATION

IL METODO DI PIEGATURA DEGLI ORIGAMI INCONTRA LE TRAME DI LINO

#1 1/3 LENZUOLO
60x112
-FRONTE RETRO USUALI

#2 FEDERA
47x71
-FRONTE RETRO USUALI
-FRONTE CON RICAMI

ESEMPI Progetto Procida (Liberti, Fiorentino, Cirillo)

1. Conclusions

The partners agree that the overall result of the meeting is very satisfactory, given that all items on the agenda were covered and a successful work plan has been implemented.